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Economic and environmental implications of the nuclear power phase-out in Belgium: Insights from time-series models and a partial differential equations algorithm

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ABSTRACT

By 2025, Belgium will phase-out nuclear power. Unassessed so far, this policy reform may modify the economic and environmental channels through which energy and society interfere in this country. In this paper, we investigate whether this structural energy change may adversely impact the growth of the Belgian economy (i) and its ability to meet its long-term greenhouse gas emission targets (ii). A multivariate model comprising production factors (labor, capital, and exports), nuclear and renewable energy uses, total primary energy supply, economic growth, and CO₂ emissions from the power and heating sector is combined with real time-series data spanning the 1974–2019 period. The analysis consists in sequentially assessing two distinct nexuses (energy-economy and energy-economy-environment) over reduced- and augmented frameworks (excluding and including nuclear energy), and through a two-stage empirical strategy: time-series econometric estimations (Toda-Yamamoto causality test, Impulse Response Functions (IRFs), and the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lags (ARDL) and Machine Learning (ML) experiments with a Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) algorithm. For robustness purposes, we conduct two seminal tests which relate to dynamic predictive processes (T-Mat and Verticality tests). Besides confirming the time-series findings, our ML results highlight the necessity to timely manage the process of nuclear phase-out, along with a progressive deployment of installed renewable energy capacity. This should avoid additional economic costs, energy security threats, and undermining of climate targets. In doing so, this study combines macro-level nexus investigations with the politics and institutional determinants of nuclear energy reliance and seeks to bring inclusive knowledge on this topic.

1. Introduction

Global warming is a burning issue to be addressed with high priority. This problem is largely attributable to the elevated combustion of fossil

fuels driving the release of harmful pollutants in the atmosphere, which, in turn, increases the global surface temperature (Zhang et al., 2011). According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2014), one should expect a 4.8 °C increase in global surface temperature

Abbreviations: AI, Artificial Intelligence; ANNs, Artificial Neural Networks; ARDL, Auto-Regressive Distributed Lags; ARIMA, Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average; CO₂, carbon dioxide; CSP, Concentrated Solar Power; DL, Deep Learning; DOLS, Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares; DTR, Dynamic Treatment Regimes; ECM, Error-Correction Model; ECT, Error-Correction Term; EKC, Environmental Kuznets Curve; FE, Fixed Effects; FEVD, Forecast Error Variance Decomposition; FMOLS, Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares; GC, Granger Causality; GDP, Gross Domestic Product; GFCF, Gross Fixed Capital Formation; GHG, Greenhouse Gas; GMM, Generalized Method of Moments; IPPC, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change; IRFs, Impulse Response Functions; ITE, Individualized Treatment Effect; LAC, Latin America and Caribbean; LSTM, Long Short-Term Memory; LVEM, Lotka–Volterra Ecosystem Model; MG, Mean Group; ML, Machine Learning; PDEs, Partial Differential Equations; PPC, Pedroni Panel Cointegration; PWGC, Pair-Wise Granger Causality; RE, Random Effects; SUR, Seemingly Unrelated Regression; TY, Toda–Yamamoto; VECM, Vector Error Correction Model; WC, Wavelet Coherence.

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by 2100, inducing a 0.82 m rise in sea level, and substantial effects on natural ecosystems and population in coastal areas (Lau et al., 2009).

In this view, advanced and emerging economies currently face a burning challenge. On the one hand, they seek to answer their growing sectoral energy demands in more secure and efficient energy procurement. On the other hand, they committed to reducing Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions associated with the generation of power required by the economic activity (Menyah and Wolde-Rufael, 2010). While renewable energy has emerged as unavoidable to curb carbon dioxide emissions (CO₂) in the long-run, nuclear power remains a non-negligible strategy as it provides a low-carbon supply of power (Magazzino et al., 2022; Vincent et al., 2020; Özübuğday and Erbas, 2015; Menyah and Wolde-Rufael, 2010; Adamantiades and Kessides, 2009; Elliot, 2007; Ferguson, 2007). For this reason, emerging economies (notably China, India, and Brazil) show a strong interest in this energy source as it can reinforce their energy security and reduce their dependence on fossil fuels in the generation of power while allowing substantial emissions savings (IEA, 2008). In this view, Toth and Rogner (2006) argued that expanding nuclear power is viable in emerging countries that have a booming energy demand and a significant risk of oil and gas reserves scarcity. Finally, it can provide solutions to economies characterized by substantial barriers to renewable energy development (Fiore, 2006), while providing a transitional or permanent solution to decarbonize current energy supplies in the new climate era (Ting and Lin, 2021).

Nonetheless, one must admit that it contradicts the recent energy decisions made in Belgium. In the wake of the Fukushima nuclear accident in March 2011, controversial discussions arose in Europe and led to drastic nuclear energy pattern reforms (Wittneben, 2011). As a highly complex technology, nuclear power is seen as a double-edged bet because it raises important concerns regarding its operational safety and radioactive waste disposal, as well as the health threats it poses for future generations (Toth and Rogner, 2006). In consequence, closing-down policies set before the Fukushima disaster have been accelerated in Germany (by 2022) and Switzerland (by 2034) (Kunsch and Friesewinkel, 2014). Regarding Belgium, the phase-out program was first launched in 2003. After 40 years of operating time, it foresaw the closure of seven Belgian nuclear power plants by 2015 (Belgian Federal Government, 2003). Since the 1970s, policymakers have relied on this resource to meet the growing power demand. Unlike the traditional dominance of polluting fuels in most countries, nuclear power has dominated the Belgian electricity mix over the past decades. Therefore, Belgium remains heavily dependent on it. Another constraint stands in its current commitment to address the elevated levels of polluting emissions. In line with the European Union (EU) long-term strategy, Belgium aims to become an economy with net-zero GHG emissions by 2050 (European Commission, EC, 2020). For the above reasons, nuclear-related decisions remain highly interlinked with national security, geopolitics, and democracy types (Ting and Lin, 2021). While geopolitical interests may increase the likelihood of adopting nuclear energy, electoral democracy and broader civil participation generate diverging pressures on nuclear reliance, notably because of their institutional nature (Ting and Lin, 2021). For this reason, the nature of the nuclear-Gross Domestic Product (GDP)-CO₂ emissions nexus may endogenously respond to institutional evolutions.

Here, we sustain that phasing-out from nuclear will pose non-negligible challenges for this country, starting with jeopardizing the existing economic and environmental targets (D'haeseleer, 2003). Initially, a provision in the law allowed for a renegotiation of the shutting-down schedule in case of significant energy supply safety threats. Thus, the government first extended the operational license permits of the oldest nuclear power plants to 2025 (IEA, 2016). Then, several studies were also commissioned by the government, even before the Fukushima event, to ensure the technical feasibility of the reform (Ampère, 2000). While they all suggested further postponing the shut-down deadline, in 2012 government rejected a new time extension and maintained the 2025 phase-out plan (Kunsch and Friesewinkel, 2014).

Nonetheless, these studies expressed crucial reserves that cannot be neglected. Notably, they pointed out that nuclear abandonment might induce electricity production deficits, risk of power supply shortage, and considerable carbon footprint degradation.

Given that the ongoing nuclear program has low operational costs and is almost completely decarbonized, policymakers decided to operate a challenging trade-off between replacing nuclear-based power by “bridging” fossil fuels (coal and natural gas), importing power from foreign suppliers, or expanding renewable energy plants (IEA, 2020b). However, it is worth highlighting that power-based nuclear requires a substantial amount of water, by contrast to wind and solar. Going one step further, Žohar and Snoj (2019) showed that activated cooling water in nuclear facilities can present a significant radiation source around primary cooling system causing radiation damage to electrical components, increasing doses to personnel and additional heating to superconducting coils. Hence, those inferences may underestimate the net operational costs of nuclear facilities, as well as the effective scale of some externalities induced by radioactive waste treatment and management on humans and soils. Furthermore, maintenance costs, which are typically accounted for differently than operating costs, do exist and matter. For instance, Koomey and Hultman (2007) conducted a reactor-level analysis of busbar costs for US nuclear plants from 1970 to 2005. They showed that the projected busbar costs for new reactors in a favorable regulatory environment are at or below the costs of the cheapest reactors within the historical sample starting in 1970's. Although reactor designs have been standardized, licensing procedures have been streamlined, and construction management techniques are much more sophisticated than before, some old problems remain, and new ones may emerge, which in turn, makes the maintenance cost challenge of nuclear facilities even more compounded. This issue turns non-negligible when dealing with aging plants, and highlights the persisting trade-off between bearing plant decommissioning costs or covering time-increasing maintenance expenses for energy planners. In an attempt to further identify those inferences, Gohel et al. (2020) offered a predictive maintenance architecture development for nuclear infrastructure using Machine Learning (ML) tools. Also, the outcome of relying on a temporary bridging fuel (i.e., power-based natural gas) remains conditional to a careful design of a transition policy. Although they provide better operational flexibility, non-renewable sources are carbon-intensive (Destek, 2016; Solarin and Shahbaz, 2015). And, since the power and heating sector accounts for more than 25% of the national emissions (oil, natural gas, and oil cover more than 39% of the total power output) (WDI, 2020), the risk of considerably deteriorating Belgian carbon footprint is real. Then, importing electricity from foreign suppliers is conditional on the existence of available foreign capacities and the efficiency of interconnected transport grids. Finally, deploying renewable energy might appear highly relevant as it displays low-carbon characteristics. However, low-carbon energy facilities require substantial fixed costs, R&D technologies (especially with regard to the latest technologies: Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) involving mirrors and solar thermal storage based on molten salt technologies; floating wind turbines which offers the advantage of less obtrusive installations; printable organic solar cells using semiconducting inks printed directly onto flexible stretchable thin plastic or steel; biomass gasification technologies using a gasifier system converting solid biomass into clean combustible gas) as well as resources and technical skills, making investment decisions more difficult for many firms (Shahbaz et al., 2013; Beck and Martinot, 2004). Thus, straightening out the current investment climate (through transparency, predictability, and regulatory certainty) cannot be neglected anymore (IEA, 2020b). In addition, a relatively long window of time is necessary to allow alternative energies to reach a substantial share in the total electricity mix and replace the nuclear provision of power. Particularly for the case of Belgium, the development of alternative energies faces significant technical constraints, such as the low land elevation (making the deployment of hydropower and pumping storage stations limited), the high population

density (11 million inhabitants for a total surface of 30,500 km² making the available surface for implementing on-shore windmills insufficient), and the short coastline of the territory (making the potential of offshore wind farms restricted).

Consequently, while renewable energy resources represented only 20.8% of the total electricity output (including 0.5% from hydroelectric sources) in 2015 (WDI, 2020), the most optimistic predictions estimated that low-carbon energy sources may reach (a maximum of) 35% of the total electricity production (32 TW/year). As a result, providing extra-power capacity to cover the nuclear plants' closure is crucial. It has been estimated at 1100 MW per year by the Belgian Federal Planning Bureau. For this reason, Kunsch and Friesewinkel (2014) suggested that nuclear should be considered as a transition fuel until renewables become sufficiently significant and competitive.

In the light of these elements, the Federal government will have to address a crucial dilemma at the crossroads between energy, economic, and environmental objectives. Focusing on four principal objectives, the “New Energy Pact” proposed by Belgian decision-makers is challenging. First, it aims at ensuring a secure supply of power (considering the growth of electricity demand). Second, it seeks not to contradict the global climate action set under the Paris agreement ratified in 2015 and imposed a 35% GHG emissions reduction by 2030 (with respect to 2005) (UNFCCC, 2015). Third, it pledges to maintain an affordable energy cost for businesses and families, essential for economic performance and societal wellbeing. Fourth, it comprises a secure phase-out nuclear plan including substantial decommissioning budget and radioactive waste treatment processes. Accordingly, the Belgian nuclear phase-out raises important concerns about potential economic losses and threats to sustainability that it might induce. Our explicit aim is to bring consistent answers to these issues in the present study.

An in-depth review of the literature underlines four crucial gaps that our paper seeks to fill in a simultaneous manner. Above all, to the best of our knowledge, no study explicitly examined the nuclear energy-GDP nexus for the singular case of Belgium, which is believed to present insightful features for policy purpose. In addition, we could not find any previous assessment of the energy-environmental linkages for this specific case study, although such nexus has been extensively investigated elsewhere. This is surprising since the 2025 nuclear phase-out recently endorsed can substantially affect the fragile macro-economic and environmental trends, while threatening the power supply and energy security targets of this country. Besides, there is a lack of understanding of the complex process of policy change throughout various periods in the Belgian phase-out policy. The nuclear power phase-out topic is tightly linked with the energy transition process (Edberg and Tarasova, 2016). However, few studies examined the issue from a social sciences perspective (Sovacool, 2014), forgetting that energy transition shares evident political process features (Geels, 2011). Therefore, tightly linked with Ting and Lin (2021), this study offers an in-depth assessment of the Belgium case as it is characterized by a singular institutional setting, which may have early determined the phase-out policy, and underlyingly increased its economic and environmental implications. Furthermore, when looking at previous empirical studies, most published works on the causal link between nuclear energy consumption and economic growth considered large and various samples of countries. Moreover, only a few of these panels harbor Belgian data: Saidi and Omri (2020) for 15 organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries; Omri et al. (2015) for a group of 17 diverse countries; Al-Mulali (2014) for 30 major nuclear-energy-consuming countries; Richmond and Kaufmann (2006) for 36 OECD and non-OECD countries. However, discussions are going on whether including highly heterogeneous economies in a multi-country panel estimation procedure can bring consistent generalizable results to each member. Inversely, in the light of Magazzino et al. (2020a) for Switzerland, Vincent et al. (2020) for Korea, Luqman et al. (2019) for Pakistan, Dong et al. (2018) for China, Payne and Taylor (2010) for the US, a single-case estimation using time-series data is more likely to provide valuable country-specific

insights useful for policymakers. This is where our paper finds its first contribution. Thus, there is a point in investigating the nature and direction of causalities characterizing the nexus between nuclear-based electricity consumption, economic performance, and CO₂ emissions from the power and heating sector for the case of Belgium.

Our second novelty aspect is methodological. Even though the most recent research considers CO₂ emissions data, results remain conflicting. This is primarily because empirical methods (Fixed Effects, FE; Random Effects, RE; Mean Group, MG; Auto-Regressive Distributed Lags, ARDL; Vector Error-Correction Model, VECM) or causality tests (Granger, 1969, 1988; Toda-Yamamoto, TY), data periods, and samples selected (OECD, EU; advanced/emerging economies; nuclear-energy-consuming countries) sharply differ among studies, thus introducing heterogeneous conclusions on identical questions, with a poor potential of comparability (Schneider, 2022). While findings are hardly comparable, their policy implications might be misleading. Hence, this calls for further inquiry into this topic using several recent methodologies in tandem. Thus, our second contribution concerns the implementation of a complete causality testing framework followed by a new ML procedure. Particularly, we employ the TY procedure that does not require a pre-test for cointegration. This procedure avoids bringing any possible bias into the analysis via an Error-Correction Term (ECT). Besides testing the robustness of the econometric findings, the Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) algorithm inspects the causality inferences that operate within a multivariate framework. Using advanced data testing methods derived from Artificial Intelligence (AI), they go beyond a simple forecasting purpose and overcome the common econometric bias reported in the literature, notably: inappropriate cointegration models (Perman and Stern, 2003); inadequate specification of variables in a Granger model (Stern, 2011); inter-dependent time-series (Bruns and Gross, 2013); tendency to over-fit VAR models in small samples (Bruns et al., 2014).

Third, a strand of the nuclear energy-GDP literature relied on bi- or tri-variate approaches (when carbon emissions data is included) to perform such analysis (Jin and Kim, 2018; Chu and Chang, 2012; Yoo and Ku, 2009; Yoo and Jung, 2005). When data availability constraint arises, they do not avoid the risk of omitted variable bias and false causality estimations. Besides incorporating environmental indicators, this paper provides a third novelty aspect to the literature in including production factors (labor and capital) as additional variables. Finally, in line with Shahbaz et al. (2013), we check the importance of exports of goods and services in the estimated model. As shown in Helpman and Krugman (1985), they are thought to share non-negligible linkages¹ with economic changes in Belgium.

Fourth, we implement a systematic approach for including nuclear energy in the framework. Existing studies either use only nuclear power (Menyah and Wolde-Rufael, 2010; Payne and Taylor, 2010), or nuclear and renewable energy (Kartal, 2022; Vo et al., 2021; Apergis et al., 2010), or fossil fuel and nuclear power (Dong et al., 2018) together. Thus, this paper contrasts to previous ones as we propose and apply an econometric specification with total energy use and share of nuclear energy, which is thought to avoid some multi-collinearity bias and may provide more plausible estimates for Belgium. Then we consider the role of renewable energy in the ML part, separately.

In sum, by 2025, Belgium will phase-out nuclear power. Unassessed by previous empirical assessments so far, this policy change may modify the economic and environmental channels through which energy and society interfere in this country. Indeed, the phase-out is a recurring discussion topic that can draw substantial investment uncertainties for renewable energy market players (de Frutos Cachorro et al., 2020). In the face of this challenge, this paper seeks to bring inclusive knowledge

¹ Exports can increase the total factor productivity, improve technology transfer, enhance skills workers, and total production capacity (Rivera-Batiz and Romer, 1991; Grossman and Helpman, 1990).

on an overlooked and unassessed case study so far: Belgium. Our paper seeks to fill multiple gaps of the literature in a simultaneous manner. It is the first study examining whether future nuclear energy conservation policies might adversely impact the growth of this economy (i) and its ability to meet its long-term GHG emission targets (ii). To do so, a multivariate model comprising production factors (labor, capital, and exports), nuclear and renewable energy uses, total primary energy supply, economic growth, and CO₂ emissions from the power and heating sector is implemented over the 1974–2019 period. Our analysis aims at sequentially assessing two distinct nexuses (energy-economy and energy-economy-environment) on reduced- and augmented frameworks (excluding and including nuclear energy), and using a two-stage empirical methodology (time-series economic analysis and ML experiments). Having performed the TY causality test, Impulse Response Functions (IRFs), and ARDL model, we develop and apply an innovative PDEs algorithm. For robustness purpose, we conduct two seminal tests which relate to checking the consistency of dynamic predictive processes (T-Mat and Verticality tests). We use causality in the sense of Granger throughout the paper.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the relevant literature. Section 3 describes the data and the two-steps methodology. Section 4 displays and discusses the empirical results. Section 5 gives concluding remarks and nuclear phase-out policy recommendations.

2. Literature review

Research on the nexus among nuclear energy consumption, economic growth, and carbon emissions has attracted a substantial body of literature. Often through extensive multi-country assessments, mixed pieces of evidence have been brought to qualify the nature of this relationship. The Belgian case has been only considered within large and heterogeneous panels and thus remains overlooked. As done for other economies, this study might bring country-specific insights, useful for policymakers. We first present relevant single-country assessments on the linkages between nuclear energy, economic growth, and carbon emissions (2.1). Then, we review the multi-country investigations of this topic that included Belgium as a panel member (2.2).

2.1. Nuclear energy-economic growth-carbon emissions nexus: country-specific evidence

Several country-specific pieces of evidence related to various nuclear countries have been provided in the literature. One striking observation derived from this survey of single-country investigations of the nuclear energy-GDP-CO₂ emissions nexus is the absence of Belgian-related empirical assessments.

A seminal attempt to estimate the role of this energy source in mitigating environmental pollution has been conducted by Iwata et al. (2010) for the case of France. Under the context of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) from 1960 to 2003, they relied on the pair-wise Granger causality tests. As a result, strong evidence of a one-way causality running from nuclear to carbon emissions reduction in this country was found. Meanwhile, their findings supported the EKC hypothesis. Focusing on the US, Menyah and Wolde-Rufael (2010) documented the existence of a unidirectional causality running from nuclear energy to CO₂ emissions, but not vice versa. However, no linkage is found between nuclear energy and GDP growth. Payne and Taylor (2010) revealed the absence of a causal link among variables, congruent with the “neutral hypothesis”. This is in line with Jaforullah and King (2015), who confirmed the neutral impact of nuclear power on carbon emissions in the US. In Dong et al. (2018), the authors assessed the dynamic relationship between per capita fossil fuels consumption, per capita nuclear energy consumption, per capita renewable energy consumption, per capita GDP, and per capita CO₂ emissions for the case of China. Empirical findings indicate that nuclear and renewable energy

consumption play essential roles in reducing environmental pollution, although the effective impact of nuclear on CO₂ emissions is far smaller than renewables. Mahmoud et al. (2020) supported the existence of bidirectional causality between nuclear energy and carbon emissions. Thus, nuclear power is found to elevate CO₂ emissions and vice versa. Lastly, starting from the consideration that Switzerland will phase out nuclear power by 2034, Magazzino et al. (2020a) examined the nuclear energy consumption-economic growth nexus in this economy. To do so, they newly complemented the standard time-series approach (econometric causality tests) with an ML (ANNs) process. Findings reveal a bidirectional relationship and argued in favor of the careful implementation of the phase-out policy in this country. Table 1 outlines the primary information of this literature.

2.2. Multi-country studies (including Belgium) on the relationship among nuclear energy consumption, economic growth, and CO₂ emissions

While never assessed with a single-country approach, Belgium has often been included in large panels testing the relationship between nuclear energy consumption and economic growth, including sometimes carbon emissions in the framework. Here, we identified nine multi-country studies matching this description. To save space, notice that macro-level panel studies excluding Belgium are not reported in the summary Table 2 below. However, for an exhaustive review of this topic, we recommend Ozturk (2010) and Shakeel (2021).

The first empirical evidence on the aforementioned nexus can be traced back to Richmond and Kaufmann (2006). They considered 36 OECD and non-OECD countries to test whether there is a turning point in the relationship among income, energy use, and carbon emissions. Panel RE results show that nuclear energy significantly reduces carbon emissions, validating the EKC hypothesis for OECD countries only. Apergis and Payne (2010) documented a long-run equilibrium relationship

Table 1
Summary of previous single-country studies on the nuclear energy-GDP-carbon emissions nexus.

Author(s)	Countries	Data Period	Methodology	Causality
Iwata et al. (2010)	France	1960–2003	PWGC	NE→(-)C
Menyah and Wolde-Rufael (2010)	US	1960–2007	GC, FEVD	NE⇌Y and NE→(-)C
Payne and Taylor (2010)	US	1957–2006	TY	NE⇌Y
Jaforullah and King (2015)	US	1965–2012	VECM, GC	NE⇌C
Dong et al. (2018)	China	1993–2016	ARDL, VECM, DOLS, FMOLS	NE→(-)C
Mahmood et al. (2020)	Pakistan	1973–2017	ARDL, VECM, G.C.	N.E. ↔C
Magazzino et al. (2020a)	Switzerland	1970–2018	G.C., TY, ANNs	NE→Y

Source: our elaborations.

Notes: NE, Y, and C represent nuclear energy consumption, economic growth, and CO₂ emissions, respectively. NE→(-)C: an increase in nuclear power consumption is associated with a decrease in CO₂ emissions. NE⇌Y: no causal relationship between nuclear energy consumption and economic growth (“neutral hypothesis”). NE→(+)C: an increase in nuclear power consumption is associated with an increase in CO₂ emissions. Y→NE: unidirectional causality from economic growth to nuclear energy consumption (“conservation hypothesis”). NE↔C: bidirectional causality between nuclear energy consumption and carbon emissions. NE↔Y: bidirectional causality between nuclear energy consumption and economic growth (“feedback hypothesis”). ANNs: Artificial Neural Networks; ARDL: Auto-Regression Distributed Lag; DOLS: Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares; FEVD: Forecast Error Variance Decomposition; FMOLS: Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares; GC: Granger Causality; PWGC: Pair-Wise Granger Causality; TY: Toda-Yamamoto; VECM: Vector Error Correction Model; WC: Wavelet Coherence.

Table 2
Summary of previous multi-country studies (including Belgium) on the nuclear energy-GDP-CO₂ emissions nexus.

Author(s)	Countries	Data Period	Methodology	Causality for Belgium (if ≠ from the other panel members)
Richmond and Kaufmann (2006)	36 OECD and non-OECD countries	1973–1997	FE	NE→(-)C
Apergis and Payne (2010)	16 countries	1980–2008	PPC, GC	NE→Y
Nazlioglu et al. (2011)	14 OECD countries	1980–2007	GC, TY	NE⇌Y
Al-Mulali (2014)	30 major nuclear energy-consuming countries	1990–2010	VECM, GC	NE→Y and NE→(-)C
Baek (2015)	12 OECD countries	1980–2009	FMOLS, DOLS	NE→(-)C (LR)
Omri et al. (2015)	17 mixed countries	1990–2011	GMM	NE→Y
Apergis et al. (2019)	19 mixed countries	1984–2007	ECM, GC	NE→Y
Saidi and Omri (2020)	15 OECD countries	1990–2018	FMOLS, VECM	NE→Y and NE⇌C
Pao and Chen (2020)	5 advanced countries	1987–2016	LVEM, ARIMA	Negative elasticity between NE and C

Source: our elaborations.

Notes: NE, Y, and C represent nuclear energy consumption, economic growth, and CO₂ emissions, respectively. NE→(-)C: an increase in nuclear power consumption is associated with a decrease in CO₂ emissions. NE⇌Y: no causal relationship between nuclear energy consumption and economic growth (“neutral hypothesis”). NE→(+)C: an increase in nuclear power consumption is associated with an increase in CO₂ emissions. Y→NE: unidirectional causality running from economic growth to nuclear energy consumption (“conservation hypothesis”). NE↔C: bidirectional causality between nuclear energy consumption and carbon emissions. NE↔Y: bidirectional causality between nuclear energy consumption and economic growth (“feedback hypothesis”). LR means that the mentioned relationship was found significant in the long run only. ARIMA: Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average; DOLS: Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares; ECM: Error Correction Model; FE: Fixed Effects; FMOLS: Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares; GC: Granger Causality; GMM: Generalized Method of Moments; LVEM: Lotka-Volterra Ecosystem Model; PPC: Pedroni Panel Cointegration; TY: Toda-Yamamoto; VECM: Vector Error Correction Model.

among real GDP, nuclear energy consumption, real gross fixed capital formation, and the labor force for 16 countries. In addition, panel Granger causality test (Granger, 1969, 1988) supported the feedback hypothesis, indicating the existence of bidirectional causality between nuclear energy consumption and economic growth. This is in line with Apergis et al. (2010), who showed that nuclear energy consumption plays a vital role in reducing CO₂ emissions for 19 diverse countries, whereas renewable energy consumption does not. In addition, a bidirectional causality between nuclear energy consumption and economic growth is established, congruent with the “feedback hypothesis”. Nazlioglu et al. (2011) determined that the direction of causality between nuclear energy consumption and economic growth for 14 OECD countries is neutral, highlighting that no causal linkages are depicted among variables. Nonetheless, the use of the TY causality test (Toda and Yamamoto, 1995) revealed contradictory results. The “neutrality hypothesis” emerges for some countries, including Belgium. Based on a series derived from 30 major nuclear-consuming countries, Al-Mulali (2014) revealed that nuclear energy consumption has a positive

short-run causal relationship with GDP growth, while a negative short-run causal relationship with CO₂ emission. This corroborates Baek (2015), who supported that nuclear power reduces carbon emissions in 12 major nuclear energy generating countries. Using a slightly different estimation method (i.e., dynamic simultaneous-equation panel data models), Omri et al. (2015) inspected the nuclear energy-renewable energy-economic growth nexus. Results of the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) exhibited the existence of a unidirectional causality running from nuclear consumption to economic growth for Belgium and Spain only. Recently, Saidi and Omri (2020) asked whether nuclear energy consumption matters in reducing carbon emissions in the OECD. While results demonstrated that nuclear power consumption causes CO₂ emissions reduction in the short- and long-runs, country-specific estimates rejected this assertion for Belgium. Lastly, Pao and Chen (2020) operated a methodological break with the standard literature, analyzing the influence of nuclear energy on economic activity and environmental degradation. For the five countries they selected (France, Belgium, Sweden, Switzerland, and the US), the Lotka–Volterra Ecosystem Model (LVEM) confirmed that the compound annual growth rate of CO₂ emissions, CO₂ intensity, and energy intensity are negatively linked. Findings indicated that nuclear power is one of the most important energy sources for achieving absolute decoupling and genuinely sustainable development. Table 2 summarizes the main information of this nuclear-related literature.

Finally, it is worth previous empirical assessments which considered Latin America on this topic. For instance, Ozturk (2017) inspected the impact of alternative and nuclear energy consumption, fossil fuel energy consumption, carbon dioxide emissions and oil rent on economic growth and foreign direct investment in the panel of 9 Latin American countries, for the period of 1975–2013. Results of Pooled Seemingly Unrelated Regression (SUR) indicate that nuclear and fossil energy consumption are associated with positive GDP per capita responses, while oil rents fail to promote economic growth in the region. With respect to individual countries, nuclear energy significantly increases GDP per capita of Colombia, Peru, and Venezuela only, but fails to do so in other countries of the sample. Later, Ben Mbarek et al. (2018) replicated this analysis for 18 developed and developing economies, including Argentina, Brazil, Greece, India, Iran, Romania, Turkey, Venezuela and Pakistan. However, results derived from Granger causality tests failed to supply evidence of a significant causal link between nuclear energy consumption and GDP, in line with the “neutral hypothesis”. Earlier, Naser (2015) claimed that there exists a long-run dynamic relationship among oil prices, nuclear energy consumption and GDP in Russia, China, South Korea, and India, as suggested by the Johansen (1991) cointegration approach. More generally, Hanif (2017) explored the influence of fossil fuel consumption, power energy consumption, oil-based imports and environmental degradation in Latin America and Caribbean (LAC) countries. System-GMM findings offered evidence supporting the existence of an inverted U-shaped curve characterizing the relationship between per capita GDP and carbon emissions from fuel combustion. Also, Wolde-Rufael (2005) led a seminal stone on the energy demand-GDP topic in Africa, later followed by Bello and Ch’ng (2022) who offered the first evidence of energy intensity convergence across African countries using β - and stochastic-convergence tests. Namahoro et al. (2021) finally examined the impact of energy intensity, low-carbon energy, and GDP on CO₂ emissions across African regions and income levels. IRFs and Forecast Error Variance Decomposition (FEVDs) outputs revealed that both energy intensity and economic growth counted higher variations of CO₂ emissions, while renewable energy highly contributed to reducing emissions within 10 years. For an exhaustive review of the causality and determinants of energy and electricity demand in the Southern Africa countries, see Inglesi-Lotz and Pouris (2016).

Using a slightly different approach, Llanos et al. (2022) broadened the research on the use of neural networks in conjunction with causality techniques for economic policy development. Starting from an

unbalanced sample of 94 countries between 1971 and 2018, the authors presented a methodological framework that employs the transformation of time series into a set of treatment intervals according to potential policies that a country may implement. They combined treatment intervals, with a multiclass classifier to obtain propensity scores, and Neural Networks (Long Short-Term Memory, LSTM). Associated results showed that grouping countries according to income level, mid-low and low levels of income have better development under moderate growth policy with respect to levels of carbon emissions and energy consumption, supporting the EKC hypothesis. In the same vein, [Michell et al. \(2022\)](#) proposed a framework to enhance the forecasting performance of high-frequency electricity consumption data. To do so, they employed both ML and econometric models (ARIMA and Holtz-Winters) to account for time-dependence in the data series. Results clearly showed how LSTM models outperform all other available statistical procedures, including a conventional ARIMA approach. Finally, [Pandelara et al. \(2022\)](#) applied a wavelet approach with fuzzy regression analysis to capture the causal relationship between energy consumption and GDP for 61 countries and with various time-scales spanning the 1990–2014 period. This enabled the authors to offer a wide set of policy recommendations connected to the fuzziness description of the data.

This literature review on the relationship among nuclear energy, economic performance, and environmental pollution highlights three important points.

- First, while a range of studies conducted valuable single-country assessments, none of them considered the specific case of Belgium. Bringing Belgian-related evidence is crucial since the Federal government scheduled a complete abandonment of nuclear power by 2025.
- Second, we underlined that large panels of countries attempted to include Belgian data within their samples. However, evidence on the nature of the interactions among nuclear power, economic activity, and carbon emissions are mixed, sometimes conflicting, and often hardly comparable.
- Third, the methodologies employed sharply differ, ranging from panel estimation techniques to causality procedures, but also stochastic trend cointegration, testing models and wavelet spectral analysis. Moreover, until [Magazzino et al. \(2020a\)](#), ML evidence was non-existent on this topic, although they have demonstrated powerful capacities on neighbouring questions ([Magazzino et al., 2020a, 2020b, 2020c](#)). This paper seeks to fill the above-mentioned gaps in an innovative way.

3. Data sources and variables' definitions

We collected nuclear energy generation and renewable energy generation (both in TWhs) data and total primary energy consumption (ExaJoules converted to TWhs) series from the British Petroleum Statistical Review of World Energy² (BP, 2020) as a proxy for nuclear energy consumption. Also, data on CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion in the power and heating sector (thousand tonnes) are compiled and taken from the IEA CO₂ Emissions from Fuel Combustion Statistics³ (IEA, 2020a). This indicator proxies the environmental pollution induced by power generation. Finally, we collected data on Gross Domestic Product (constant 2010 US\$), Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF, constant 2010 US\$), population (total) and exports of goods and services

² Nuclear energy consumption data and total primary energy consumption series are available at: <https://www.bp.com/en/global/corporate/energy-economics/statistical-review-of-world-energy.html>.

³ Data on CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion in the power and heating sector are available at: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/energy/data/iea-co2-emissions-from-fuel-combustion-statistics/co2-emissions-by-product-and-flow_data-00430-en.

(constant 2010 US\$), as a proxy of economic growth, capital, labor force, and exports. All series are taken from the World Development Indicators database⁴ (WDI, 2020). Data spans the entire nuclear Belgian program (from opening the first plant to the most recent period): 1974–2019. The series are used in their natural logarithms to avoid non-Gaussian distributions. Data definitions, data sources, and variable descriptions are summarized in [Table 3](#).

This paper employs a two-stage methodology: time-series econometrics (i) and ML experiments (ii). In the former approach, we first assess the energy-economy nexus and perform the Toda-Yamamoto causality test on a K-L-TPE production function, an export-augmented K-L-TPE specification, and a nuclear-augmented K-L-TPE framework. Then, an identical causality testing strategy is applied on the energy-economy-environment nexus, for the following two distinct models: CO₂-GDP-TPE framework, and nuclear energy-augmented CO₂-GDP-TPE specification. Besides, this analysis is complemented with variance analyses (IRFs) to examine the consistency of the above relationships ahead of the selected sample period. Followingly, we develop and apply a new AI algorithm based on PDEs. For robustness purposes, we conduct two specific tests relating to dynamic predictive processes (T-Mat and Verticality tests). [Fig. 1](#) outlines our complete stepwise causality testing approach.

For the preliminary analysis of the energy-economy nexus, we adopt a Cobb-Douglas production function framework with three factors of production: $GDP = f(K, L, E)$.

We consider the log-linear form of the function and alternative specifications regarding the energy input, *E*. We start with total energy use (TPE) to show the relative importance of the energy input. Then we consider a specification that uses nuclear energy (NEC) and renewable energy (REC). This specification is problematic due to severe multicollinearity. Hence, we adopt an alternative specification with total energy use (TPE) and nuclear energy (SNE) share. We proceed with the following main framework to examine the impact of nuclear energy

Table 3
Data description.

Indicator	Acronym	Measure	Source
Total primary energy consumption	TPE	ExaJoules (converted to TWh)	British Petroleum Statistical Review of World Energy (BP, 2020)
Nuclear energy consumption	NEC	TWh	British Petroleum Statistical Review of World Energy (BP, 2020)
Renewable energy consumption	REN	TWh	British Petroleum Statistical Review of World Energy (BP, 2020)
GDP	GDP	Constant 2010 US\$	World Development Indicators (WDI, 2020)
CO ₂ emissions from fuel combustion (electricity and heating production)	co2	thousand tons	iea CO ₂ emissions from fuel combustion statistics (iea, 2020a)
labor force	l	total population	world development indicators (wdi, 2020)
Gross Fixed Capital Formation	K	Constant 2010 US\$	World Development Indicators (WDI, 2020)
Exports of goods and services	EXP	Constant 2010 US\$	World Development Indicators (WDI, 2020)
Share of nuclear energy	SNE		SNE=NEC/TPE

Source: our elaborations.

⁴ GDP, labour force, capital, and exports data are available at: <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>.

Fig. 1. Stepwise two-stage causality testing methodology. Source: our elaborations.

share on carbon emissions:

$$CO2 = f(GDP, K, L, TPE, SNE)$$

We work again with a log-linear function for empirical analysis of this energy-environment-economy nexus.

For the time-series analyses, we consider the TY procedure as our main method.⁵ The TY procedure does not require testing for cointegration and estimation of the cointegrating vector. This is an advantage over ECMs (i.e., Johansen-Juselius, ARDL), because in ECMs a possible bias in the estimated cointegration vector is brought back into the analysis as the ECT. TY avoids this by relying on a lag-augmented VAR($k + d$) in levels. The optimum lag length (k) is determined via some information criteria. The lag augmentation (d) is done according to the highest order of integration of the series in the VAR. The modified Wald test on the joint significance of the first k lags is a test for long-run Granger causality because all variables in the system are in levels. The test statistics follow a χ^2 distribution with k degrees of freedom. The VAR ($k + d$) is as in Eq. (1):

$$Y_t = \alpha + \beta_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_{k+d} Y_{t-k-d} + \varepsilon_t \tag{1}$$

where Y contains the variables in the model, α is an $n \times 1$ vector of constants (n is the number of variables), β_i is an $n \times n$ matrix that contains the coefficients, and ε_t is for residuals that follow a white noise process. Following the evolution of the empirical literature, we first consider some preliminary models.

4. Time-Series framework and empirical findings

Stationarity properties of the series are checked via several commonly used unit root tests (PP, ADF, ERS, NP z -alpha, and GLS detrended ADF), and one test that allows breakpoints (VP); the results are reported in Table 4.

Results from the first five tests in Table 4 are the same for GDP , K , and TPE , but slightly contradictory for L , NEC , and EXP series. Traditional

tests (ADF and PP) – which have low power in small samples – find all series to be stationary when first differenced. However, tests with a higher power, such as NP, GLS, and ERS provide contradictory results to traditional tests for L , NEC , and EXP series. GDP , K , TPE , and REC appear to be integrated of order one. When we consider the unit root tests with breaks, L is found to be $I(1)$, and the evidence suggests that NEC and EXP may be stationary in levels. Hence, the time-series characteristics of the series render the application of methods that require the same level of integration inappropriate. Hence, we proceed with the TY procedure, but also check robustness with ARDL.

4.1. The energy-economy nexus⁶

4.1.1. K-L-TPE production function

For our first preliminary model, we consider a framework with a three-factor production function, $GDP(K, L, TPE)$ to see how important energy use is for Belgium. Hence, here there are $n = 4$ variables in the system depicted in Eq. (1). Regarding the lags' selection, three of the five criteria indicate k to be 4 and the unit root test results indicate that $d = 1$. The VAR(5) satisfies the stability condition in that all roots are within the unit circle. For brevity, only the GDP equation is depicted in Eq. (2) below:

$$GDP_t = \alpha_1 + \sum_{k=1}^5 \beta_{1k} GDP_{t-k} + \sum_{k=1}^5 \beta_{2k} K_{t-k} + \sum_{k=1}^5 \beta_{3k} L_{t-k} + \sum_{k=1}^5 \beta_{4k} TPE_{t-k} + \varepsilon_{1t} \tag{2}$$

where α_1 is the constant term, β_{ik} denotes the coefficient of variable i at lag k ($i = 1$ to 4, $k = 1$ to 5), and ε_{1t} is the white noise error term in the GDP equation. When we check for autocorrelation, the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test indicates a slight autocorrelation, but the Ljung-Box Q-statistics do not show any significant problem at any lag. The χ^2 value

⁶ We do not present detailed results for this nexus to save space. They are available from the authors upon request.

⁵ We check the robustness of TY results by an ARDL method.

of 22.4712 (P-Value = 0.0002) for the joint significance of the first 4 lags of *TPE* indicates that *TPE* Granger causes GDP.⁷ For *K*, the test statistic is 9.7915 (P-Value = 0.0441) and for *L* it is 15.1463 (P-Value = 0.0044). This indicates that the traditional factors of production, capital, and labor also Granger cause GDP in Belgium. It is worthwhile to note that *TPE* has a larger statistic (lower P-Value) than *K* and *L*, indicating the relative importance of energy in the economy.^{8,9}

4.1.2. Exports-augmented *k-l-tpe* production function

The second preliminary model extends the first one by adding exports to Eq. (2). Hence, the overall framework is now *GDP(K, L, TPE, EXP)*. This can be viewed as a check for possible omitted variable bias. When *EXP* enters the picture the lag augmented system becomes VAR(1 + 1).¹⁰ The TY procedure does not indicate any causality running from *K, L, TPE, or EXP* to GDP at conventional significance levels.¹¹ Furthermore, *EXP* does not Granger cause any of the other variables in the system. This implies that *EXP* may not add much explanatory power. It is also worth noting that although the *R*² is high in the GDP equation, all variables appear insignificant. This indicates a severe multi-collinearity effect. Hence, we do not consider exports in what follows.

4.1.3. Nuclear energy-augmented *k-l-tpe* specification

The next step in the preliminary investigation is to understand the role of nuclear energy in the economy. For this, we consider two different frameworks. Following Apergis et al. (2010) we first consider *REC* and *NEC* together in our production function framework, *GDP(K, L, NEC, REC)*. Second, we add the share of nuclear energy *SNE*: *GDP(K, L, TPE, SNE)* to the VAR that is exemplified by Eq. (2).

For the nuclear and renewable energy case, the VAR(3 + 1) is chosen.¹² According to the TY procedure, neither nuclear nor renewable energy Granger causes GDP.¹³ The GIRFs confirm the causality results. GDP does not react to shocks in either *NEC* or *REC*. Here, we discover that multi-collinearity results in insignificant coefficients in the equations even though the adjusted *R*² values are high. Hence, we question the validity of this particular specification and move on to the second framework, which considers the share of nuclear power in the energy portfolio while controlling for *TPE*.

We start with testing the stationarity of the new variable *SNE* (see

⁷ We re-estimate the equations with Newey-West corrected standard errors to account for autocorrelation. The conservative estimations confirm the results of the Granger causality tests from the original equations.

⁸ We check the Generalized Impulse Responses Functions (GIRFs), which show that the impact of a one standard deviation shock to *TPE* lasts longer than that of *K* (GDP appears unresponsive to a shock in *L*). This confirms that *TPE* is relatively more important than *K* and *L*.

⁹ To check the robustness of the results with an alternative method, we use the ARDL framework. The ARDL(2,2,0,0) was selected among alternative specifications as it has the minimum Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC) value. In this specification, *K* and *TPE* appear significant, but *L* does not. We next consider the long-run form and cointegration. The *F* statistic of 19.1784 exceeds the 1% critical values of both asymptotic and finite sample upper bounds. This indicates a long-run equilibrium relationship between the variables. In the cointegration equation, *TPE* is the only long-run forcing variable for GDP. This provides support for our TY findings on the relative importance of energy use in Belgium.

¹⁰ VAR stability is satisfied. Again, Newey-West corrected standard errors are used to account for autocorrelation. Conservative model results are the same with those of the original equations.

¹¹ The GIRFs show equal importance of *K, TPE, and EXP*. GDP appears unresponsive to shocks in *L*.

¹² Three of the information criteria indicate an optimal lag length of 4, but the lag augmented VAR(4 + 1) does not satisfy the stability condition. Hence, we rely on LR test, which shows an optimum lag length of 3. No roots for VAR(4) lies outside the unit circle. When we account for autocorrelation results do not change.

¹³ This result holds even when we consider *GDP(K, L, NEC)* only.

Table 4). The *SNE* unit root tests yield contradictory results. However, there is some evidence that the series is *I*(0). Hence, we again take the maximum order of integration as *d* = 1 in the TY procedure. The causality tests are based on VAR(1 + 1), which is stable.

TY procedure results indicate that *TPE* Granger causes GDP, but the share of nuclear energy does not play a role. The GIRFs confirm this result. The framework with *TPE* and *SNE* is more in line with the preliminary results than the one with *NEC* and *REC*.

The results of the preliminary models indicate that energy is an important factor of production in Belgium. However, the share of nuclear energy may not matter for economic growth. Hence, the nuclear phase-out plan is not expected to have adverse effects on the economy.

4.2. The energy-economy-environment nexus

We proceed with the main models that focus on the environmental performance of the economy. Here, carbon dioxide emissions become the focus of our attention. In that respect, carbon emissions (CO₂) from fuel combustion in electricity generation and heating are included in the VAR model. As a natural first step, we again start with stationarity checks of the new variable, CO₂. According to three of the unit root tests (ADF, PP, and VP), the CO₂ series is *I*(1). Others indicate it does not become stationary even after second differencing. We choose to proceed with *d* = 1 for parsimony.

4.3. CO₂-GDP-TPE framework

We first consider CO₂, GDP, *K, L, and TPE*. The optimum lag length determined by Likelihood Ratio (LR) test, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Final Prediction Error (FPE), and Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion (HQIC) is 4, and the lag augmented VAR(5) satisfies the stability condition.¹⁴ Only the CO₂ equation in the VAR system is depicted in Eq. (3) below to conserve space:

$$CO_{2t} = \alpha_1 + \sum_{k=1}^5 \beta_{1k} GDP_{t-k} + \sum_{k=1}^5 \beta_{2k} K_{t-k} + \sum_{k=1}^5 \beta_{3k} L_{t-k} + \sum_{k=1}^5 \beta_{4k} TPE_{t-k} + \sum_{k=1}^5 \beta_{t-k} CO_{2t-k} \varepsilon_{1t} \tag{3}$$

In Table 5, we present the Wald test statistics for testing the null of no Granger causality for all variables in all equations (the dependent variables are in columns). We test the null hypothesis that the row variable does not Granger cause the dependent variable via a Wald joint significance test on the first 4 lags of the row variable. In the GDP equation, *TPE* remains important, since the Wald test statistic of 16.0090 (P-Value = 0.0003) is significant at 1% level. Hence, *TPE* Granger causes GDP in the long-run. Labor also Granger causes GDP with a test statistic value of 21.1858 (P-Value = 0.0003) at 1% level of significance. However, *K* has a test statistic of 6.5122 (P-Value = 0.1640), which does not allow us to reject the null hypothesis that *K* does not Granger cause GDP. Note that *K* was only marginally significant in our preliminary *KLE* model. The addition of CO₂ seems to have reduced its importance even further. Thus far, the results are in line with preliminary investigations. When it comes to the new variable, CO₂, at 10% significance level CO₂ leads GDP ($\chi^2 = 8.2230$, P-Value = 0.0837). This implies that there is feedback from the environment to the economy. Although the significance appears to be marginal, one may expect increased feedback over time due to climate change.

When we consider the CO₂ equation, we observe that GDP leads

¹⁴ Diagnostic tests (White heteroskedasticity, CUSUM, CUSUM of squared residuals, Ramsey RESET) do not indicate any problems in any of the equations. Slight autocorrelation problem indicated by LM and Q statistics is accounted for by Newey-West adjustment.

Table 4
Stationarity properties of the variables.

	GDP	K	L	TPE	NEC	REC	EXP	SNE	CO2
PP									
Levels									
Constant	-0.827	0.057	3.956	-1.072	-8.544 ^a	-0.250	-0.410	-3.134 ^b	-1.789
Const. & trend	-1.745	-2.600	-1.190	-1.686	-8.422 ^a	-2.361	-2.154	-2.446	-2.612
First Differences									
Constant	-7.559 ^a	-5.940 ^a	-7.227 ^a	-6.795 ^a	-23.089 ^a	-4.826 ^a	-8.807 ^a	-7.106 ^a	-7.742 ^a
Const. & trend	-7.711 ^a	-5.904 ^a	-10.173 ^a	-6.804 ^a	-26.097 ^a	-4.804 ^a	-9.016 ^a	-7.485 ^a	-7.682 ^a
ADF									
Levels									
Constant	-0.780	0.057	3.283	-1.070	-2.569	0.357	-0.425	-2.160	-1.682
Const. & trend	-1.755	-2.658	-1.206	-1.523	-1.583	-2.636	-2.168	-1.845	-2.317
First Differences									
Constant	-7.559 ^a	-5.941 ^a	-7.238 ^a	-6.800 ^a	-5.690 ^a	-4.631 ^a	-8.902 ^a	-2.725 ^c	-8.070 ^a
Const. & trend	-7.762 ^a	-5.904 ^a	-9.481 ^a	-6.815 ^a	-6.265 ^a	-4.940 ^a	-8.924 ^a	-2.885	-7.993 ^a
ERS									
Levels									
Constant	111.80	50.420	1.780	28.768	975.39	22.972	435.52	32.10	32.57
Const. & trend	12.605	9.167	62.622	18.043	338.28	9.951	12.512	32.89	13.97
First Differences									
Constant	22.348	1.331 ^b	15.300	8.170	351.31	1.348 ^b	6.611	11.32	10.54
Const. & trend	5.756 ^c	4.095 ^b	4.654 ^a	4.932 ^b	989.99	1.810 ^a	10.459	21.26	12.49
NP									
Levels									
Constant	1.291	1.029	-27.29 ^a	-0.526	0.530	-0.069	1.337	-1.815	-0.132
Const. & trend	-7.008	-10.93	-0.688	-4.803	-0.013	-9.397	-7.683	-6.866	-7.054
First Differences									
Constant	-1.728	-21.30 ^a	-1.249	-4.707	0.114	-20.67 ^a	-2.103	-1.328	-2.054
Const. & trend	-20.3 ^b	-21.7 ^b	-18.9 ^b	-21.0 ^b	0.633	-49.8 ^a	-20.32 ^b	-1.56	-5.68
DF-GLS									
Levels									
Constant	0.324	0.489	-0.182	-0.477	0.920	-0.27	0.850	-0.79	-0.36
Const. & trend	-1.91	-2.37	-0.701	-1.591	-0.967	-2.43	-2.108	-1.35	-2.12
First Differences									
Constant	-1.469	-5.54 ^a	-1.510	-1.86 ^c	-0.160	-3.81 ^a	-1.191	-0.996	-1.030
Const. & trend	-5.55 ^a	-5.93 ^a	-9.674 ^a	-5.67 ^a	-3.231 ^b	-5.18 ^a	-5.791 ^a	-2.250	-2.202
VP									
Levels									
Constant	-1.872	-4.011	-0.209	-3.055	-25.12 ^a	-1.659	-1.874	-5.21 ^a	-3.234
Const. & trend	-3.615	-4.340	-3.324	-3.139	-24.68 ^a	-5.67 ^a	-4.740	-6.24 ^a	-4.227
First Differences									
Constant	-9.02 ^a	-6.59 ^a	-9.504 ^a	-7.10 ^a	-25.32 ^a	-7.22 ^a	-12.33 ^a	-8.01 ^a	-8.54 ^a
Const. & trend	-8.77 ^a	-6.51 ^a	-11.79 ^a	-7.71 ^a	-25.16 ^a	-6.90 ^a	-12.05 ^a	-6.24 ^a	-9.70 ^a

Notes: Superscripts ^a, ^b, and ^c represent significance at 1, 5, and 10%, respectively. TPE stands for total primary energy use; NEC is nuclear energy use; REC is renewable energy use; GDP is gross domestic product; CO2 is carbon emissions from fuel combustion; L is labor force; K is gross fixed capital formation; EXP is exports; SNE is share of nuclear energy. Significance implies stationarity. Entries are test statistics from the following unit root tests: PP: Phillips-Perron; ADF: Augmented Dickey-Fuller; ERS: Elliot-Rothenberg-Stock Point Optimal; NP: Ng-Perron z-alpha; DF-GLS: Dickey-Fuller GLS detrended; VP: Vogelsang-Perron with structural breaks.

carbon emissions in the long-run ($\chi^2 = 9.2164$, P-Value = 0.0559) at a 10% significance level. As expected, TPE strongly causes emissions from fuel combustion in electricity generation and heating. A curious result is that L also Granger causes emissions. At first glance, this may seem peculiar, but L also leads GDP, K, and TPE. Hence, its impact on emissions may be through its strong impact on other factors of production.

Labor is Granger caused by all other variables in the model. This suggests that the energy-economy-environment nexus has a strong social impact. K is not Granger caused by any and it Granger causes only L. One can argue that capital accumulation is important for the energy-economy-environment nexus only through its impact on employment.

Overall, the dynamics of the energy-economy-environment nexus appear to be very complex and rich. The GIRFs show that none of the shocks create permanent impacts, indicating that there are no variables outside the system that drive the variables included in the system.¹⁵

¹⁵ Only CO₂ GIRFs are reported to save space, while the remaining tests are available from authors upon request. They show significant initial responses for GDP, K, and TPE to shocks in CO₂. L responds significantly to all shocks with 5 lags. K has short lived positive initial responses to GDP and TPE. TPE has positive initial responses to GDP, K, and CO₂, but a positive response to a shock in L after 5 periods. The results do not contradict with causality analysis.

Fig. 2 depicts the responses of CO₂ to generalized 1 standard deviation shocks to other variables.

We observe that emissions have a significant initial positive response to a shock in TPE, but not to GDP, K, or L. This provides partial support for the causality analysis.¹⁶

4.4. Nuclear energy-augmented CO₂-GDP-TPE model

In our preliminary investigation, we found that the share of nuclear energy does not play an important role indicating that phasing out nuclear energy will not have an adverse effect on GDP. In this section, we are mainly concerned with whether the nuclear phase-out policy in Belgium would hamper the environmental performance or not.

We consider a VAR with GDP, TPE, SNE, and CO₂ following the preliminary analysis in the nuclear energy-economy nexus and energy-

¹⁶ When we add exports as a control variable, we observe that the equations have very high coefficients of determination, but all variables in the GDP equation become insignificant. This implies severe multi-collinearity. Indeed, when we check the coefficient variance decompositions several eigenvalues are lower than 0.001 and VIF for EX is too high. Hence, exports do not improve the model, on the contrary, it deteriorates the model.

Table 5
TY modified Wald test statistics for energy-economy-environment nexus.

	GDP	CO2	K	L	TPE
GDP	–	9.2164 ^c	2.6906	14.4529 ^a	4.3119
CO2	8.2230 ^c	–	6.6324	20.8358 ^a	7.7365
K	6.5122	5.4716	–	16.0178 ^a	7.0423
L	21.1858 ^a	16.3278 ^a	3.6761	–	24.7808 ^a
TPE	16.0090 ^a	36.0446 ^a	5.0438	31.3635 ^a	–

Notes: Superscripts ^a, ^b, and ^c represent significance at 1, 5, and 10%, respectively. Entries are test statistics from the TY Granger causality test. Significance implies that the row variable Granger causes the column variable.

environment-economy nexus. The TY Granger causality test results are summarized in Table 6.

We observe that GDP and total energy use are the main long-run drivers of carbon emissions. However, the share of nuclear energy does not impact emissions in the long run. TPE and CO₂ Granger cause SNE at 1% and 5% significance levels.¹⁷ The GIRFs in Fig. 3 below confirm the neutrality of emissions to shocks in SNE.

Fig. 3 also shows the strong response of emissions to a shock in TPE, in line with our previous results.

Overall the causality tests and IRFs analysis provide three main results. First, energy is an important factor in production. Second, the share of nuclear energy does not lead to GDP. Third, the share of nuclear energy does not lead to carbon emissions. Hence, the Belgian nuclear energy phase-out will not affect the economy or the emission performance in the long run.

5. Partial differential equations model and machine learning results

This section presents the theoretical framework of the PDEs algorithm and the associated results.

5.1. Partial differential equations framework

We use a complex Deep Learning (DL) model based on nonlinear PDEs to test our time-series results. This tool requires the dynamic consideration of two NNs characterized by noise and time. The NNs will be characterized by profundity and non-linearity. Two distinct NNs are necessary to avoid differentiation in the dataset, which will remain stable but conditioned. In particular, the second will be characterized by dynamism and non-linearity, allowing us to act within a multifaceted space-time context.

We build a class-based model of nonlinear dynamic functions using a standard physics approach. Its resolution passes through nonlinear PDEs of the type:

$$\partial_t = \delta(t, x, \partial, \partial_x, \partial_{xx} \dots \partial_{x,n}) \rightarrow n^3 \dots n^n \tag{4}$$

where δ is a nonlinear function of time t ; x simulates the action space of variables.

According to Rudy et al. (2017), we generate the so-called "expansion effect" on:

¹⁷ We check the robustness of these results with the ARDL method. An ARDL (3,3,2,1) model is selected via SIC. In this model, we observe that only TPE and all of its lags are significant at 1% level. Only the second and third lags of GDP are statistically meaningfully different from zero. The contemporaneous term of SNE is significant, but its lag is not. The F statistic of the bounds test exceeds the 1% critical values for both asymptotic and finite sample critical values. This indicates there is a cointegrating relationship between the variables. All variables in the cointegrating equation are highly significant. In the long-run GDP and SNE reduce emissions, whereas TPE has a positive effect. In this case, the ARDL results contradict with TY results. Hence, we proceed with the ANN for further insight.

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(t, x, \partial, \partial_x, \partial_{xx} \dots \partial_{x,n}) = & \gamma_{0,0} + \gamma_{1,0}\partial + \gamma_{2,0}\partial^2 + \gamma_{3,0}\partial^3 + \gamma_{0,1}\partial_x + \gamma_{1,1}\partial\partial_x \\ & + \gamma_{2,1}\partial^2\partial_x + \gamma_{3,1}\partial^3\partial_x + \gamma_{0,2}\partial_{xx} + \gamma_{1,2}\partial\partial_{xx} + \gamma_{2,2}\partial^2\partial_{xx} \\ & + \gamma_{3,2}\partial^3\partial_{xx} + \gamma_{0,3}\partial_{xxx} + \gamma_{1,3}\partial\partial_{xxx} + \gamma_{2,3}\partial^2\partial_{xxx} \\ & + \gamma_{3,3}\partial^3\partial_{xxx} + Y_{n,n}\partial^n\partial_{n \rightarrow n} \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

In (5) $x = (x_1, x_2 \dots x_m)$, where m is a vector acting in a dimension characterized by the second derivatives of the sets: $\partial_x \dots \partial_n$.

We solve (5) through Gordon's equation process. In this way, we can join the NN to the nonlinear partial equations:

$$\delta = \aleph = \varphi \tag{6}$$

$$\varphi \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + V\psi = 0 \tag{7}$$

$$\hat{H}\psi = E\psi, H = T + V = \frac{p^2}{2m} + V \rightarrow p = \psi \vec{\nabla} \tag{8}$$

$$E^2 = m^2 + p^2 \tag{9}$$

$$-\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} = m^2 \psi - \nabla^2 \psi \tag{10}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \cdot \\ xt \\ \cdot \\ z \\ \cdot \\ o \\ \cdot \\ n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cosh \theta & -\sinh \theta \\ \sinh \theta & \cosh \theta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} xt \\ z \\ o \\ n \end{pmatrix} \tag{11}$$

Now, we use n -Gradient in

$$x^n = (x^0, \bar{x}) \rightarrow \partial_m = \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}, \vec{\nabla} \right) \tag{12}$$

$$\partial_m \partial^m = \rho^{mv} \partial_m \partial_v \tag{13}$$

Then, we solve (10) in (13):

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} \partial \\ xt \\ \vec{\nabla} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \partial \\ \vec{\nabla} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \tag{14}$$

$$\rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} \partial \\ xt \\ \vec{\nabla} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} \\ -\vec{\nabla} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \square^2 = \frac{\partial \psi^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla \tag{15}$$

$$\square^2 \psi + m\psi = 0 \rightarrow (\square^2 + m)\psi = 0 \tag{16}$$

According to Baydin et al. (2018), we approximate (16) in an NN:

$$(\square^2 + m^2)\psi = f : \rightarrow \delta - \aleph(t, x, \partial, \partial_x, \partial_{xx} \dots \partial_{x,n}) \tag{17}$$

In (17) the parameters of the NN in a Gordon model can be estimated as:

$$SSE := \sum_N^i \left(\left| \partial(t^i, x^i) - \delta^i \right|^2 + \left| f(t^i, x^i) \right|^2 \right) \tag{18}$$

where t^i, x^i, δ^i are the training and testing data on δ .

The difficulty of elaborating a PDEs algorithm is to represent the function of \aleph . In fact, we could solve the equations through a solution of the partial type. However, mathematically it would appear partially correct. The reason for a partial result lies in the learned function (\aleph). It presents itself as yet another unknown, and we do not know its functional form. Therefore, at present, there is no mathematical model capable of solving partial equations of this type. At most, the use of the

Fig. 2. Responses of CO₂ to 1 generalized Standard Deviation shocks to GDP, K, L, and TPE. Notes: our elaborations in EViews.

Table 6
TY modified Wald test statistics for nuclear energy-economy-environment nexus.

	GDP	CO2	TPE	SNE
GDP	–	12.5124 ^a	1.1504	3.8157
CO2	13.0370 ^a	–	2.3065	10.1829 ^b
TPE	5.4602	43.9775 ^a	–	27.4706 ^a
SNE	2.1946	2.0511	5.4930	–

Notes: Superscripts a, b, and c represent significance at 1, 5, and 10%, respectively. Entries are test statistics from the TY Granger causality test. Significance implies that the row variable Granger causes the column variable.

spectral method comes to mind. However, his solution does not apply to this paper. Therefore, we decide to solve the equations through the Raissi et al. (2017) approach.

In other words, we use solvers where the nonlinear function (N) is known and circumscribed within the domain of an NN. So we use the Burgers (1948) equation in Raissi et al. (2017) implemented in Oryx, with PINN and Myrrix application.

5.2. Machine learning results

We develop a single extensive causality test of two distinct NNs capable of predicting each variable’s nexus used in the econometric model. Therefore, the mathematical solution takes the following form:

\mathbb{N}^n our NNs with n hidden unit; f^n NN in PDEs; G^n is GDP; Ne^n is NEC; S^n is SNE; T^n is TPE; R^n is REC; C^n is CO₂; E^n is EX.

$$\text{Thus, } f^n \in \mathbb{N}^n \rightarrow G^n, Ne^n, S^n, T^n, R^n, C^n, E^n \rightarrow 0 \text{ and } n \rightarrow \infty \quad (19)$$

Then, $f^n \rightarrow \partial$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

If we consider $(G^n, Ne^n, S^n, T^n, R^n, C^n, E^n) = \pi$ we can write $\pi \in R^d$ with $\pi \partial \sim \text{Time}(T) = \pi \partial_T = (0, T) \times \pi$ (Raissi, 2018).

So, we can observe the results where we add L^2 -error between

solutions of the Burgers’ equation and causal relationship in the PDEs (Table 7).

Table 7 reports the results of our ML approach. The ML model, adapted to PDEs, applies an inductive approach to the econometric standard. Furthermore, our process uses an algorithm capable of optimizing and improving the dataset’s representation, which is considered a large aggregate of data. Besides, the algorithm – written in Oryx and adapted to Myrrix – used “unsupervised learning”. In doing so, our approach examines the data for alternative patterns by generating code that can recognize those new patterns in new data. In total, the initial algorithm was adapted from 49 new ML algorithms in which relevant information is extracted from the data without being explicitly programmed (Myrrix). Table 7 reports 21 direct and bidirectional causality results concerning (19). Each causation has four outcomes: ITE^a, Vorticity, Viscosity, and L^2 -error. The first column (Individualized Treatment Effect, ITE) originates from DL models’ predictive test optimized for Minkowski error. The second column represents the self-regulation nexus of n variables in a HAM dimension process. If this test is identical in the direct and bidirectional causal link, the link between the two variables considered is defined as “strong”. Its value must always be less than 1.5 (they are regarded as thousandths of a second) and can have a negative value. In some cases, a sense of causality could give a positive value and the same value but with a negated sign. In this case, we speak of an “inversely strong” bond. The viscosity test simulates the Dynamic Treatment Regimes (DTR) test, usually used in physics ML approaches to test two similar fluids’ viscosity. We have used this test to reinforce or not the causal links obtained through data adaptation. Its value to be valid must be greater than 1. If the bidirectional causal links show identical stickiness values, the ML model becomes “compact”. Finally, the last column shows the L^2 -error test. It represents the model’s goodness and derives from solutions of the Burgers’ equation.

Our ML model results confirm, in part, the econometric ones and, in some cases, reinforce their significance. In Table 8, we report a summary of the best training results of the four tests.

Fig. 3. Responses of CO₂ to 1 generalized Standard Deviation shocks to GDP, TPE and SNE.

Notes: The continuous lines are generalized impulse responses and dotted lines are confidence bands. Confidence band above 0 indicates significance.

There is a solid two-way causal link between GDP and renewable energy consumption. The ITEⁿ test shows that as GDP grows over time, renewable energy consumption increases by a value of between 2.7 and 2.9. This result confirms the predictive form of the model from the GDP side. It is interesting to note how the bidirectional sense presents a “strong” and “compact” result. The bi-directional values of the vorticity and viscosity tests have identical values (0.7 vs. -0.7) (1.2 vs. 1.2). The second result, the nexus between GDP and CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion, shows us an interesting sense of bidirectional causality. In this case, we note that the “strength” and the “compactness” about the model are identifiable with values lower than those of the previous causal link. This result highlights a very interesting association between the variables. In particular, we can note that the Vorticity test shows a negative identity value in the bidirectional sense (0.7 vs. -0.7). Getting such a result is a rare event. In other words, the algorithm shows us how, in an ITEⁿ equal to 2.2, a reduction in CO₂ emissions could favor “strong” processes on the growth of the GDP of Belgium. Analyzing Table 8, we note a two-directional sense of causality of order 1 (understood that the algorithm presence or strong or compactness). These results can be traced back to $S^n \rightarrow T^n, T^n \rightarrow R^n, T^n \rightarrow C^n$. Among the causal relationships analyzed by our algorithm, a relevant role is provided by the bi-directional result between renewable energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. We note the simultaneous presence of “strength and compactness”. In this case, we report the negative sign in the vorticity test (-0.8). This result deserves an explanation. The algorithm, analyzing an ITE between 2.7 vs. 1.8, underlines how an increase in renewable energy consumption influences a reduction in CO₂ emissions. We compare this result with the link in Table 7 between nuclear energy consumption (Ne^n) and CO₂ emissions (C^n). There is no sense of “strong and compact” in this relationship in our tests. We, therefore, can interpret this result by saying that renewable energies are considerably more effective than nuclear power in reducing carbon emissions from electricity generation. Hence, nuclear power cannot be considered adequate as an energy technology to reduce polluting emissions (at least CO₂).

Besides, our model suggests aiming to reduce their renewable energy emissions rapidly. Since renewables seem much more effective for reducing carbon emissions worldwide, critical negative implications emerge for nuclear energy. Technologically, nuclear systems have been prone to higher construction costs, delays, and longer lead times than renewable energy projects. Hence, countries planning large-scale investments in new nuclear power risk suppressing the significant climate benefits of investing in alternative renewable energy.

The validation of our algorithm requires two specific tests relating to dynamic predictive processes. The first represents the so-called T-Mat test (Fig. 4), the second is the Verticality test (Fig. 5). Concerning the T-Mat test, it analyzes the positioning of the algorithm in a hypothetical hyperbolic plane. The analysis uses a time parameter ranging from 0 (the starting point) to a maximum of 10 (the end of the algorithm processing). On the other hand, the fluctuations are analyzed in a range that goes from -1 to +1. Values tending to -1 represent a loss of redundancy in the analysis process. Instead, values tending to +1 represent moments of non-supervision of the algorithm. The representation of a linear plane gives the optimal value of the test without fluctuations.

As we can see from Fig. 4, our algorithm passes the validation of the T-Mat-test. The fluctuations are present only in the initial phase of the elaboration. Besides, they are only fluctuations tending to +1 (even if the maximum value is +0.84). The fluctuations are gradually decreasing to zero in the short run. The whole algorithm processing process is perfectly distributed in a linear plane.

The Verticality test uses the heat cascade model. In other words, the whole process of ML analyzes the sequences by attributing a degree of temperature to hypothetical errors in the processing. The test considers on the ordinate axis the time (in seconds) ranging from 0 to 2 s and represents the maximum processing time of the algorithm. On the abscissa axis, the recombination process of the binary programming levels is shown. Moreover, in this case, the values vary from 0 to 2. Within the analysis, however, the temperature level of the process is represented. It

Table 7
ML results.

Average computation: $G^n \rightarrow Ne^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.7	0.7	0.3	1.13e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.3	0.1	0.1	1.14e+08
Average computation: $G^n \rightarrow S^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.6	0.9	0.4	1.13e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.1	0.2	0.2	1.12e+02
Average computation: $G^n \rightarrow T^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	3.4	1.2	1.1	2.29e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.2	0.1	0.2	1.13e+02
Average computation: $G^n \rightarrow R^n$ *				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.9	0.7	1.2	5.34e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	2.7	0.7	1.2	5.30e-02
Average computation: $G^n \rightarrow C^n$ **				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.3	0.5	1.1	4.38e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	2.2	-0.5	1.1	3.83e-02
Average computation: $G^n \rightarrow E^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.1	0.7	0.9	2.98e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.7	0.4	0.8	2.62e-02
Average computation: $Ne^n \rightarrow S^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	0.2	0.1	0.1	1.33e+02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.1	0.2	0.2	1.32e+02
Average computation: $Ne^n \rightarrow T^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.0	2.0	2.0	1.48e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	2.1	1.8	1.7	1.44e-02
Average computation: $Ne^n \rightarrow R^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.4	1.8	1.2	3.33e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	2.2	1.7	0.9	3.27e-02
Average computation: $Ne^n \rightarrow C^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	1.9	2.0	1.7	4.84e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.1	0.8	0.2	2.87e+02
Average computation: $Ne^n \rightarrow E^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.4	2.8	2.4	1.23e+02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.1	0.3	0.4	1.11e+02
Average computation: $S^n \rightarrow T^n$ *				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.9	1.8	1.6	5.54e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	2.11	1.8	0.8	4.43e-02
Average computation: $S^n \rightarrow R^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.1	1.5	0.9	2.23e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	1.4	1.3	0.8	3.84e-02
Average computation: $S^n \rightarrow C^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.7	0.4	0.5	3.44e+02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	1.4	0.1	0.1	3.66e+02
Average computation: $S^n \rightarrow E^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.0	2.0	2.0	1.44e+02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.1	0.2	0.2	1.55e+02
Average computation: $T^n \rightarrow R^n$ *				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.1	0.2	0.4	1.22e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	1.8	0.2	0.3	1.33e-02
Average computation: $T^n \rightarrow C^n$ *				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.6	0.5	1.7	5.55e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.4	0.3	1.7	1.02e-02
Average computation: $T^n \rightarrow E^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.1	2.4	0.2	1.23e+02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.4	0.4	0.1	6.23e-02
Average computation: $R^n \rightarrow C^n$ **				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.7	0.8	1.8	4.43e-02

Table 7 (continued)

Average computation: $G^n \rightarrow Ne^n$				
Bidirectional Causal Effect	1.8	-0.8	1.8	4.25e-02
Average computation: $R^n \rightarrow E^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.1	0.3	0.7	1.56e+2
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.3	0.8	0.4	1.26e+02
Average computation: $C^n \rightarrow E^n$				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	1.2	2.0	2.1	1.22e+02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.7	0.9	0.1	4.23e+02

Notes: our elaborations in Oryx.

ITEⁿ: represents the causal prediction concerning n additional units of time. It has an almost theoretical value. Vorticity: this test tests the transport equations to train the LSTM network in the HAM dimension. Viscosity: This test simulates a DTR test usually used in physics in ML approaches.

* : Vorticity or Viscosity bidirectional causality identification.

** Vorticity and Viscosity bidirectional causality identification.

Table 8

Summary of ML results.

Average computation: $G^n \rightarrow R^n$ **				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.9	0.7	1.2	5.34e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	2.7	0.7	1.2	5.30e-02
Average computation: $G^n \rightarrow C^n$ **				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.3	0.5	1.1	4.38e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	2.2	-0.5	1.1	3.83e-02
Average computation: $S^n \rightarrow T^n$ *				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.9	1.8	1.6	5.54e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	2.11	1.8	0.8	4.43e-02
Average computation: $T^n \rightarrow R^n$ *				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.1	0.2	0.4	1.22e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	1.8	0.2	0.3	1.33e-02
Average computation: $T^n \rightarrow C^n$ *				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.6	0.5	1.7	5.55e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	0.4	0.3	1.7	1.02e-02
Average computation: $R^n \rightarrow C^n$ **				
	ITE ⁿ	Vorticity	Viscosity	L ² -error
Causal Effect	2.7	0.8	1.8	4.43e-02
Bidirectional Causal Effect	1.8	-0.8	1.8	4.25e-02

Notes: our elaborations in Oryx.

Fig. 4. T-Mat test.

Notes: our elaborations in Java.

should never be homogeneous at a theoretical level, but instead, represent areas where the process temperature varies as the processing changes.

Fig. 5. Verticality test.
Source: our elaborations in Java.

As we can see from Fig. 5, our model highlights two main areas. The first area in the upper left corner (which corresponds to the value of 0.7–0.0; 0.0–0.6) represents the beginning of the processing of our algorithm. In this phase, the analysis finds relationships between the variables considered in an ML process. However, the surrounding areas show binary values not yet subject to the analysis of our algorithm (light areas). Finally, the goodness of this test is amply documented by the final area (0.3–2; 2–0.4). In this area, the process shows infinite stages of the temperature variation of the algorithm calculations. In this way, we can affirm that the elaboration's initial phase did not represent the final one, excluding the “temporal custom paradox”. This represents a novel contribution to the literature, and one of the key novelties supplied by this paper.

6. Concluding remarks and policy implications

The ongoing nuclear phase-out in Belgium, to be completed by 2025, triggers important questions such as whether future nuclear energy conservation policies might adversely impact the growth of the Belgian economy (i) and its ability to meet its long-term GHG emission targets (ii). Unassessed so far, this policy change may modify the economic and environmental channels through which energy and society interfere in this country. Also, phasing-out may draw substantial investment uncertainties for renewable energy market players (de Frutos Cachorro et al., 2020). In the face of this challenge, this paper seeks to bring inclusive knowledge on an overlooked and unassessed case study.

Results from the TY causality test, further confirmed by IRFs and ARDL, demonstrated that primary energy consumption is an essential driver of economic growth in Belgium. However, the influential role of nuclear energy use is much less potent and turn negligible. Congruent with the literature, our time-series findings showed that GDP and primary energy consumption drive carbon release in Belgium. In contrast, nuclear energy does not significantly explain the trend of pollution. Accordingly, our econometric procedure suggests that the nuclear phase-out might neither adversely lead the economy's growth nor threaten the emission reduction target in the long run. This explanation should be viewed cautiously for several reasons. First, this paper aims to assess the impact of an ongoing nuclear phase-out policy, not some planned policy in the future. Secondly, the estimated coefficients are interpreted based on the assumption that the historical relationship between the variables will hold in the future. This assumption may be critical, especially in light of technological developments and global events like the war between Ukraine and Russia. In this regard, the overall interpretation is based on the premise that it remains economically profitable and technologically feasible in Belgium to replace nuclear power with renewable and alternative energies. That is, it is worth highlighting that the historical dynamics that shaped the energy-

economy-environment response-functions over time play out in practice.

Nonetheless, because of historical data availability constraints, the present study relied on the constraining assumptions that present observations reflect past ones. Thus, the relevance and quality of the results presented above are conditional to the state of technologies and application of future policy instruments, along with more political phenomena such as national elections, climate (non-)awareness, and the state of the energy debate regarding gas imports for present benefits and future carbon costs. Naturally, we concur that analyzing historical energy experiences helps draw lessons for the future. For an exhaustive review of the lessons from energy history and climate policy (what we can and cannot assume when it comes to technological change, demand, and economic development), we recommend Fouquet (2016a). Also, in an overview of historical energy transitions in Europe (speed, prices, and structural system transformations), Fouquet (2016b) showed that the fastest historical sector-specific energy transitions did not overcome thirty years. However, the author also acknowledged that full energy transitions, involving the complete vector of sectors and services constituting European economies, required an extended period. Ultimately, the relative price of energy services seemed to have driven the overall trajectory of old energy demand and substitution towards a more modern one. Still, one must remember that energy price shocks may have acted as energy transition-enablers. An additional argument pointed out by the author is the potential likelihood of new energy technology adoption, which seems correlated with the set of characteristics and advantageous features they encompass for the consumer. This not only sets up the conditions for a promising market (even when the initial price is relatively higher than the average cost per unit) but offers the possibility for declining industries to adapt to a modified structure of the energy demand. In this paper, we agree that such underlying historical patterns are relevant and may condition the final accuracy of our empirical results.

Outcomes from our PDEs processes confirmed and expanded the conclusions mentioned above. Here, we reaffirm that Belgium is an energy-dependent economy that, in turn, substantially influences atmospheric pollution. In particular, the predictive form of the GDP model exhibits a leading role for renewables but not for nuclear. While primary energy is found to significantly increase the level of pollution, renewable energy and nuclear power present mitigation capacities that are non-negligible. However, our algorithm simulations emphasized a counter-intuitive element: the impact of nuclear power on carbon emissions is revealed to be far much smaller than for renewables, which contradicts with a strand of the pro-nuclear literature (Chung and Kim, 2018; Dong et al., 2018; Bauer et al., 2012; Sailor et al., 2000). Hence, it is likely that renewable energy, besides inducing significant economic spinoffs, displays a larger environmental potential than nuclear over a long period. It is thus striking how energy and society interfere through the economic and environmental channels.

Therefore, practical policy recommendations can be proposed to guide the nuclear phase-out in Belgium. Laying behind the abandonment of nuclear, renewable energies are at the core of this transition process. Compared to nuclear, they trigger more economic benefits, allow for more carbon emissions savings, are more flexible, and sharply reinforce the security of the energy supply. Thus, a temporal balance is necessary to adequately handle the shutting down of nuclear power plants, on the one hand, and the deployment of installed renewable electricity capacities, on the other hand. Inversely, mismanaging this timely process would have serious consequences. To operate and deliver climate benefits, renewable energy sources require time, capital costs, and technologies. If the shutting of nuclear power plants is conducted too quickly, a power gap will emerge. Unfulfilled by domestic alternative resources, this lack would be followed by massive energy imports (mostly carbon-intensive) from foreign suppliers to avoid electricity shortages (Allcott et al., 2016). Undoubtedly, counterintuitive outcomes might then be drawn from this situation: economic costs, investment

opportunities losses for renewables, energy security weakening, and environmental targets threats. Therefore, significant infrastructure investments should be conducted along with a timely managed renewable expansion. As emphasized in [Jorge and Hertwich \(2014\)](#), it is of high importance for Belgium to upgrade transformers, power lines, and the overall capacity of its national grid to sustain the double challenge of phasing from nuclear and shifting towards renewables over a relatively constrained period.

Moreover, political decisions regarding energy policies influence broader societal development. Tightly linked with [Ting and Lin \(2021\)](#) outcomes, this study conducted an in-depth assessment of the Belgium case as it is characterized by a singular institutional setting which may have early determined the phase-out policy, and underlyingly triggered the economic and environmental implications estimated above. It has been shown that electoral democracy tends to preserve nuclear power, whereas civil society participation and deliberative democracy are likely to trigger more changes ([Ting and Lin, 2021](#)). Thus, analyzing a phase-out policy through a panel of countries may lose its consistency because its decision is partly determined by singular institutional characteristics which in turn, influence the time management of the measure and the magnitude of the impact generated by this political shock on key national indicators. In doing so, this study combines macro-level nexuses investigations with the politics and institutional determinants of nuclear energy reliance and seeks to bring inclusive knowledge on this topic.

Furthermore, in many commodity importing countries (including several members of the EU), the economic recovery underway after the great crisis due to the Covid-19 pandemic, together with the tensions between Russia and Ukraine, have caused the sharp increase in tariffs of electricity and gas forcing political parties to redesign their agendas, opening up again to the discussion on the use of nuclear power as a bridging fuel towards energy security and low-carbon development ([Magazzino and Mele, 2022](#)). The increase of natural resource prices which followed this conflict invoke new studies on their forecast, and to what extent historical data can reflect future trends.

Future research should also carefully take into account the energy transition process (from fossil to renewable sources) and its effects on the rest of the national economy, especially in terms of employment and the reshape of labor factor.

Finally, the use of advanced ML experiments, which is becoming predominant on neighbouring topics, should be systematized to check and extend time-series findings. When dealing with phase-out policies, there remains a critical gap between analytical geopolitical investigations and empirical macro-econometrics assessments. It is up to novel methodologies to build a bridge between those two strands of literature and further introduce institutional indicators within economic frameworks. So far, this research question remains sharply overlooked ([Magazzino et al., 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Mele and Magazzino, 2020](#)).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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